

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: Today, the ability to know foreign languages is becoming one of the integral parts of professional education. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, there is a high demand for them to learn the language.

Keywords: Teaching , important component , existing knowledge system , new level by using multimedia ...

In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important component of professional education. People learn such knowledge first at school, college, lyceum, and then at institutes, training courses or independently by getting acquainted with the basic information sets that help to learn a foreign language. Today, there are large collections of educational materials for people with different levels of language skills. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical methods and skills of teachers. The ability to use information technologies and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials. By combining different methods, the teacher is able to solve specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers and students should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, the ability to choose the most effective methods to achieve one's goals is formed. The use of several methods of teaching and learning will give effective results. Teaching is carried out in small steps and is based on the student's existing knowledge system. A whole set of methods is selected based on the goals of a particular student or group. We do not set ourselves the task of being fashionable and using only modern teaching methods. When preparing for international exams, fundamental and classical methods work better in combination with linguo-sociocultural and communicative methods, if you need to master the language in a short time - intensive methods, if you want to achieve a well-balanced result and you need is what is. ready to spend a little more time - communication techniques are perfect for you! Many different educational methods have been developed throughout human history. Initially, all methods of teaching foreign languages were taken from programs designed for teaching Latin and Greek, the so-called "dead languages", in which almost the entire educational process was reduced to reading and translation. The classical

approach is based on the understanding of the English language as a real and complete means of communication, that is, it is necessary to systematically and harmoniously develop all language components - oral and written speech, listening, etc. among students. The classical technique makes the English language partly an end in itself, but this cannot be considered a disadvantage. Such a comprehensive approach is primarily aimed at developing students' ability to understand and create speech. The methodology includes training with Russian teachers, but such a procedure (although not very "fashionable") cannot be considered a minus: a non-native teacher analyzes and compares two language systems, has the ability to compare constructions, convey better information, explanation of grammatical rules, warning about possible mistakes. The general enthusiasm for foreign specialists is a temporary phenomenon, because the Western world has highly valued the priority of bilingualism (knowledge of two languages). In today's world, the greatest value is represented by teachers who can think in a bicultural context and impart a relevant body of knowledge to students. Preparation of additional text topics using the press, periodicals, mass media, internet materials can be given as homework. Students will be interested in texts about interesting research and scientific discoveries. In conclusion, it should be said that teaching a modern language is aimed at forming a more cultured person, who has the skills of self-analysis and systematization of new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of the modernization of the entire system. This ensures that teachers can familiarize themselves with the most advanced approaches and then integrate them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system. Many organizations are moving to a new level by using multimedia capabilities to send and receive information. The use of computers and other devices determines the success of the entire educational process.

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